

ISic3703

I.Sicily inscription 3703

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

plaster

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Melita

Place of origin (modern)

Malta

Provenance

Rabat, arcosolium of hypogeum 13, catacombs of SS. Paul and Agatha

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Rabat, Malta, in situ

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI178087

1. [— — — — — — — — — —]
2. γερουσιάρχης φιλεντόλι [ος]
3. καὶ Εὐλογία πρεσβυτήρα ἢ αὐτοῦ σύμβιος.
- 4.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

PHI 178087

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 35.0995

Noy, D. 1993. Jewish inscriptions of Western Europe. Cambridge. At no.163

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